

The reaction of war veterans on the situation in the world.

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Annotation: This article discusses postwar aftermath. Mostly covers point of view of war veterans who came back from the frontiers of the WWII and talked about the devastating result of the war. Many of them revealed unfair and injustice attitude of military authorities towards a simple soldier. American soldiers in history were regarded as the savers and those who freed Europe from violent Nazi machine however some writers talked about soldiers who did want to be in the front, because for them war did not mean anything. Many other issues were covered in the article as well the generation that came after the war.

Key words: post war aftermath, patriotism, establishment, youth strikes.

The 20th century was a century of conflicts. Never before in the history of mankind had there been that many nations at war, fighting each other with huge armies and weapons of mass destruction. The two World Wars and the ideological battle between East and West had a huge impact on the social and political world. Many of today's conflicts can be traced back to the great wars and years that followed them, in which the nations involved tried to find a new balance and world order.

The USA took part in several significant wars and at that time is the last remaining super-power in the world. Of all the conflicts, the US was involved in, its role in the Second World War and the war in Vietnam are the two most vividly remembered. Throughout history, people have constructed and displayed a sense of their past, their collective memory and cultural knowledge through works of art. In the twentieth century, this process of myth-making has been fulfilled mainly by novels and movies. Many of these "vehicles of memory" have portrayed the wars and captured the

atmosphere in America at that time. Yet, there is a big difference in the way and the extent to which WW II and Vietnam have been digested in the conscience of the nation. Although the Second World War affected more families directly and more Americans fell in those years than during the war in Vietnam, there seems to be a tendency to suppress the memories of the latter. It is only in times of crisis (as the conflicts in Afghanistan and Iraq) that the nightmarish image of "Vietnam" appears in media commentaries and political speeches and becomes a topic of public awareness¹⁷. What is the reason? What role did literature play in the process of coming to terms with the terrible experience of wars? Which lessons do writers of war literature offer in terms of dealing with present or future conflicts?

After the WW II within a couple of years, the US had transformed into the most powerful nation on earth, while other countries involved in the war had to invest billions to rebuild their cities and their industry. It is not surprising that a war of such magnitude was very often represented in literature. In the United States alone more than four hundred novels about the war have been published between 1940 and 1973. Of course, some of these novels were mere combat adventures or propaganda novels of limited literary value and some did not manage to give the reader perspectives on and ideas about life and war that had not already been in the focus of literary discourse. We may say that the writers who witnessed the horrors of the war and survived its dangers came back home with pockets full of battle experience and stories to tell to the world. We call such writers veterans of the war, who gave their own unique trustful vision of what American army represented and experienced. Among them are Irwin Shaw, J.D Salinger, Isaac Asimov, James Jones, Kurt Vonnegut, Norman Mailer, Joseph Heller, Michael Adams.¹⁸ Not only they speak about American soldier in the war but also about

¹⁷ Partisan Review, 1960, Summer, p.93

¹⁸Brossard, C (2000), *Who walk in darkness*, Herodias, London.

nationalism and racism they faced on the battlefield, fake patriotism popularized by media but also the aftermath it left. Many writers turned to black humor and absurdist fantasy.

The war had touched not only Americans, it had even worse influence on European countries as well. Turning back from battlefields British, French, Russian and even German produced amazing literature portraying life after war in their homelands. The main themes were not only about horrors of the war but more about its upshots on civilian life. War veterans from all parts of the world had to come across new ideas, technologies and new subcultures their children brought to the world.

Literature had transformed into something new inventing unique ways of describing good and evil. The bright examples of this can be found in British literature: in Golding's *Lord of the Flies*, George Orwell's *1984*, Iris Murdoch's *A Severed Head*. They were representatives of post war generation in England called *Angry Young Men*. Later, the same ideology influenced in the emerge of young French philosophers talking about the results of the war and emptiness it brought to their lives. Among them were Sartre, Camus and Marcel. Young writers formed so-called existentialism, talking about loss of one-self, alienation, trying to identify the meaning of human existence.

As we can see war had various ways of destroying one's identity and forming generations of lost people who never found their destination in life, who never found any use of themselves to the society. It does not matter how many people are involved or where it is held, *war* gives the same upshots, it damages one's identity and destroys lives. After war period and psychology was well described and understood by James Jones. His works are of a great example of social issues raised by after war youth. Let us have a close look at this. It is to say those who came after the WW II did not know what was better for them *peace or war*, therefor as one of the Jones's heroes states in the novel

Some Came Running: “Our generation – we can’t even be lost as we were never found”
,we call them *Unfound* generation.¹⁹

This flash monologue sounds like an unbiased defense of society for the American youth. They are even ready to rebel, but they do not know in the name of what and for what purpose. And further, telling the story of the “happiness” is dying at the front than returning and living a meaningless life, echoes the conclusions in Jones’ last book, *Whistle*. Veterans are sucked in a vulgar, cynical life. “And he tries to get out - he dies” (Dave). So, the heroes of the book have a dissatisfaction with their natural reality in an effort to forget themselves with the use of alcohol, drugs, sex and gambling. Jones himself had a very peculiar attitude towards games. And he explains this by the fact that during the game a person is completely disconnected from the world around him and is obsessed only with a sense of rivalry. “The illusion is created,” Jones says, “that he is temporarily removed from the problems that constantly haunt him: bills, atomic bombs, questions like *Have I lost my mind, Has humanity gone mad?* In addition, everything is clear in the game, there are certain rules. But they don't exist in life.”²⁰

War veterans taught to be honest and moral, who fought against Germans in the WWI and later the Nazi in the WWII were shocked to witness changes happening in the society after 2 great wars. They were the last who kept dignity and were loyal to traditions and observed how newbies denied life of their fathers and established new ideology based on no rules and no morality. All in all, they brought chaos to the world in the forms of hippie communities and later student revolutions.

World faced 2 great wars in 20th century however they altered from one another even in the purposes of holding the war itself. Obviously, literature had to change too. Some of the war veterans had to witness both wars and adapt to the new terms.

¹⁹ Jones J. *Some Came Running*. – N.Y.: Scribner, 1957, p.828

²⁰ Муратова Э. *Война и Мир Джеймса Джонса*. – Т.: УзГУМЯ., 2011. -95 с.

Writers who tried to express the true terrors of modern, industrialized warfare faced the problem that it simply seemed to overstrain the capacity of language to refer to reality; it failed to signify in the face of horror.²¹ It became clear that literature had to turn away from its traditional usage of language in a world where abstract words such as "courage" or "glory" lost all their earlier meaning when juxtaposed to the grotesque mountains of decaying bodies on battlefields like Verdun. The disillusionment that the writers of the so-called *lost generation* experienced during the years of war demanded a step away from traditional forms of writing. As abstract terms had lost their value in this new world, it was characterized by a clear, basic language as used by Hemingway, one of the period's most famous and arguably best writers. His style demands the participation of the reader, as the "gaps" are often more telling than the parts visible at first glance.

On a different level, there is an important difference between novels of the First and Second World War. Ellen Fitzgerald points out that "on the whole, the novelist of the second World War rebelled against the war in much more limited ways than their predecessors had against the First World War. All the World War I clichés about making the world safe for democracy were, ironically, truer in 1945 than they had ever been in the mud of France in 1918." The result was that the Second World War was widely seen as a necessary evil. A position of protest as evident in WW I literature thus became complicated, as the war could be defended on political, social and economic levels. Instead of being in the focus of protest or rejection (as it had been the case in WW I literature), this war became "almost an essential character in its own novels."

All the agreement on the necessity of the war aside, it is apparent that in retrospect, the reality of those days has been over-simplified and mythologized. As

²¹ Blair, W, Hornberger, TH & Stewart, R (1974), *American Literature: a brief history*, Scott Foresman, Glenview. Cusatis, J (2010), *Research guide to American literature: post war literature 1945- 1970*, Facts on Life, New York.

Michael Adams puts it (in his book with the telling title *The Best War Ever*): "The Second World War has been transformed into the good war, the Good War." He explains that especially in a world that has become more complex, facing solutions which are uncertain and villains less obvious, the tendency to heighten an earlier period to the position of a golden age is understandable. This way of remembering distorts reality:

"To make World War II the best war ever, we must leave out the area bombings and other questionable aspects while exaggerating the good things. The war myth is distorted not so much in what it says as in what it doesn't say. Combat in World War II was rarely glamorous. It was so bad that the breakdown rate for men consistently in action for twenty-eight days ran as high as 90 percent. Soldiers of all nations performed deeds of courage, but they also shot prisoners, machine-gunned defenseless enemies in the water or in parachutes, and raped women, including their own military personnel.²²"

Of course, propaganda was one reason for this image (for example, fifty camera men were on hand to cover Eisenhower's first step on the beaches of Normandy and instructed over which angles they were allowed to take his picture), but it is unlikely that propaganda alone was powerful enough to affect the minds of the whole public. The consistent portrayal in literature and film also played an important role in transmitting this image of the Good War to the people. As will be demonstrated later, this folklore version of WW II is especially important that the generation that went to fight in Vietnam grew up with this consistent image. Many writers as James Michener and Joseph Heller captured life during WW II, and while they chose very different ways to do so, both managed to overcome some of the restricting conventions mentioned above.

While Europe was facing the significant battles Americans who hypothetically came to help were busy by doing some useless stuff on the islands. Heller demonstrate

²² Deutsch, A (1948), *The shame of the states*, Harcourt, Ann Arbor.

such problems in his *Catch 22*, ripping off the truth about what was of the actual concern for American generals in the war. One of the most terrifying aspects of *Catch-22* is the fact that the lives and deaths of the men in Yossarian's squadron are governed not by their own decisions concerning dangerous risks but by the decisions of an impersonal, frightening bureaucracy. The men must risk their lives even when they know that their missions are useless, as when they are forced to keep flying combat missions late in the novel even after they learn that the Allies have essentially won the war. The bureaucrats are absolutely deaf to any attempts that the men make to reason with them logically; they defy logic at every turn. Major Major, for example, will see people in his office only when he is not there, and Doc Daneeka won't ground Yossarian for insanity because Yossarian's desire to be grounded reveals that he must be sane. For many soldiers war was meaningless, they did not want to sacrifice themselves to win it, while on posters and in media all over the US was something to be part of, in reality many wanted to stay alive and tried to find the ways to escape it as Yossarian. The war for many young Americans was not crucial, they did not feel the need to be part of it, because American land was never a batter field, except for Pearl harbor, the enemy did not threat their families and they did not want to participate in someone else's war. However, the generation of war veterans who saw the 1st war and understood the evil of Nazi ideology could not stay away from the opportunity to combat it. Their lives spent on war, spent for reason to make it possible for their children to live in peace, however their children did not appreciate it.

From the thing mentioned above it can be summed that American government deceived its own nation about the war building up a wrong image. The youth were confused by it, they knew that the generation of their parents were wrong about everything yet they could not offer anything instead. Thus, they alienated themselves on remote Mediterranean islands, protested the war, dropped off from schools and universities. Moreover, they abused drugs and alcohol as an escape gate from reality.

And we may ask what was the government reaction to that? The answer is very simple, they turned their addiction into the business – to be more precise the drug traffic business. The rebellion that took over the youth in Europe and America did eliminate itself. 70 % of hippies died because of drug overdose, such a popular French revolution that shook the whole world was extinguished by government and mere amendments were registered. That is to say that veterans who had a crystal vision of the politics and understood the war unfortunately did not support the youth but labeled them as a generation with no future as it eventually happened. One of the great writers to depict the world after the war and later on was James Jones, his stories were all told by the war veterans, respected journalists and writers. There is his hero's brilliant saying he had after confronting hippie community on the Greek island "If you are an example of the new age, I feel sorry for it".

The author is openly ironic about the life philosophy of young rebels, which is freedom not to work, the right to steal, freedom of sex. And, in general, notes Jones, they looked miserable, their existence was disgusting. And, nevertheless, through the cynicism and seeming carelessness, there was a deep loneliness and suffering that caused the writer endless sympathy. James wrote: "... They were a pretty unprepossessing-looking lot, not at all attractive; but somehow familiar. Then I remembered. They made me think of the pictures of the people in the German camps".²³ Thus, in 60-70th American state had huge economic boom however they failed in cultural and social development, they formed a society with money but no soul. The US faced number of youth strikes against the wars they were holding overseas. Americans won the war but they lost their youth to drugs and hipsterism. While governments were occupied building up their economy, they had no time to aid people rehabilitate the horrors of the war. Even the country with the most powerful ideology could not hold its youth in control, here I am inferring to the

²³ Holmes, JC (1952), 'This is the Beat Generation', *The New York Times Magazine*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 1-5. Holmes, JC (1952), *Go*, Thunder's Mouth Press, New York.

Soviet Union. Even in the USSR they were some deviant parts of society mostly among youngsters – they were called “stilyaghi”. It was a part of youth community striving to imitate American lifestyle. It was also some kind of rejection the norms of life which was pretty much restricted in those dark times. People used to follow strict rules, they were not given freedom of choice a lot, they had limited number of shops to buy clothes and limited number of entertainments. Those, who fall out of the system were persecuted and punished. As it follows, *stilyaghi* were the ones who did not obey. They used to listen to American music, dance like Americans and dress like Americans. They made their hair in unusual way, wore colorful shirts and pants, gathered in small groups to celebrate their difference from the others. Yet, as many of their age mates in the same US and Europe their rebellion was delusional. They challenged the society, built their lives against the *Establishment* with no knowledge of the reason they are doing it. They never concerned about their future and did not even plan it because to be truthful they had no one. Even though soviet youth was not against the *Establishment*, they somehow rebelled in their own way to differ from the previous generation sabotaging society rules by doing exactly what is forbidden. ²⁴

The issue with young generation often happens because of cultural collapses following the war, sometimes because of the lack of freedom as it happened in case of the Soviet Union or vice versa because of too much freedom when children are left to themselves. The late ones is common for the countries which strive to construct the rocky economic system and do not have enough time to teach own children morality, even basics like how to dress, how to look after oneself, how to socialize, how to make friends, how to behave and what to value in life. Afterwar American and European generation who never experienced the challenges of war, was left to itself, they parents were too busy earning money and eventually to look after their offsprings. These kids had

²⁴ Layman, R & Hipp, J (1995), *American decades 1960-1969*, Gale Research Inc, New York.

to learn everything by themselves, how to befriend, how to love. Being left in total freedom (which I do not call freedom but careless treatment) and not knowing any restrictions or the line between good and bad these kids tried everything at a very young age like sex, drugs and crime. They came to form their own rules or better to say no rules at all. Why to follow any rules when life is better without them. This ideology brought many of them to destruction, psychological instability, crime and permissiveness. Their drug addiction brought many of them to death and asylums. Truly the generation who could not find any use of themselves and serve the world, they were like cancer destroying society slowly but for good.

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